

Influence of development communication on public acceptance of infrastructure projects in Adamawa State

Gaius Jeff Yadima

Department of Mass Communication, Glorious Vision University, Ogwa, Edo State.
Orcid ID: [0009-0009-6323-6700](https://orcid.org/0009-0009-6323-6700), gaiusjeff1@gmail.com

Ezekiel S. Asemah, PhD

Department of Mass Communication, Glorious Vision University, Ogwa, Nigeria.
Orcid ID: [0000-0003-2190-0094](https://orcid.org/0000-0003-2190-0094), asemahezeki@yahoo.com

Daniel O. Ekharefo, PhD

Department of Mass Communication, University of Benin, Edo State, Nigeria.
Orcid ID: [0009-0000-8317-2569](https://orcid.org/0009-0000-8317-2569), talk2ofomegbe@gmail.com

Abstract

The researchers examined the influence of development communication on public acceptance of infrastructure projects in Adamawa State, Nigeria. The study was guided by three objectives: to determine whether residents are aware of the development communication strategies used by the government, to identify the main channels through which residents receive information about infrastructure projects, and to assess the extent to which development communication influences residents' acceptance and support of such projects. The study adopted a survey research design, using a structured questionnaire to collect data from 357 respondents across selected local government areas in Adamawa State, after accounting for 23 lost copies of the questionnaire. Data were analysed using descriptive statistics such as frequency, percentage, and mean scores. The findings revealed that residents are generally aware of government communication strategies, particularly through radio, town hall meetings, and community leaders, although awareness of digital platforms remains relatively low. Furthermore, the results showed that development communication significantly influences public acceptance and support for infrastructure projects, as residents are more likely to support initiatives they understand. However, gaps were identified in feedback mechanisms and inclusiveness, especially in reaching rural populations. The study concludes that development communication plays a critical role in enhancing public understanding, trust, and participation in infrastructure development in Adamawa State, but its effectiveness is limited by unequal access to communication channels and insufficient opportunities for citizen engagement. The study recommends that the government should strengthen digital communication efforts while maintaining traditional channels, improve feedback mechanisms for citizen participation, and adopt more inclusive communication strategies that effectively reach rural and underserved communities.

Keywords: Adamawa State, Communication Channels, Development Communication, Infrastructure Development, Public Acceptance.

Introduction

Nigeria continues to struggle with major development challenges such as weak infrastructure, slow industrial growth, and unequal access to modern innovation. In many parts of the country, roads are poorly maintained, basic facilities are inadequate, and rural areas are often left behind in development planning. These problems reduce economic productivity and limit opportunities for citizens. Although government policies and projects are introduced regularly, there is still a wide gap between what is planned and what people actually experience. One key factor contributing to this gap is communication. Musa & Aliyu (2022) explain that development does not depend only on funding and technical execution but also on how well policies and projects are communicated and understood by the public.

The Sustainable Development Goals (SDGs), introduced in 2015, provide a global framework for addressing development challenges. SDG 9 focuses on industry, innovation, and infrastructure, which are essential for national growth. Infrastructure supports transportation, trade, and access to services, while innovation improves efficiency and development outcomes. However, achieving these goals requires more than building physical structures. It also requires effective communication that helps citizens understand the purpose of projects, builds trust, and encourages participation. Without clear communication, development projects may be misunderstood, underused, or rejected by the people they are meant to benefit.

In Nigeria, infrastructure development has not been evenly distributed across regions. The North-East region has experienced severe challenges due to insecurity, displacement, and long-term neglect. Adamawa State is one of the most affected areas, where years of conflict damaged roads, public buildings, and economic structures. This situation disrupted daily life and reduced economic activities. Over time, many residents became used to poor infrastructure and developed low trust in government interventions. Abubakar (2021) notes that in post-conflict areas like Adamawa, rebuilding infrastructure requires not only physical construction but also strong communication to rebuild trust and encourage public acceptance.

Since 2019, the administration of Governor Ahmadu Umaru Fintiri has made significant efforts to improve infrastructure in Adamawa State. These efforts include road construction, rehabilitation of existing roads, flyover projects, drainage systems, and upgrading of public facilities. These initiatives aim to improve mobility, support economic activities, and promote development in line with Sustainable Development Goal 9. However, infrastructure projects alone cannot achieve meaningful development unless citizens understand and accept them. This makes development communication an important part of the development process, as it helps to explain government actions and encourage public support.

Statement of the Problem

Despite the visible infrastructure projects carried out by the Fintiri administration in Adamawa State, many residents still do not fully understand the purpose and long-term benefits of these projects. In some communities, government projects are seen as political actions rather than genuine development efforts, which affects public trust and acceptance. Although the government uses different communication channels such as

radio broadcasts, town hall meetings, traditional institutions, and digital platforms, it is not clear how effective these strategies are in influencing public understanding and acceptance of infrastructure projects. In addition, limited community involvement and weak communication in some areas have led to poor ownership and skepticism about development initiatives, especially in a post-conflict environment where trust in government remains fragile. Therefore, there is a need to examine how development communication influences public acceptance of infrastructure projects in Adamawa State, Nigeria.

Research Objectives

The objectives of the study were to:

1. Determine whether residents of Adamawa State are aware of the development communication strategies used by the government in promoting infrastructure projects.
2. Identify the main channels through which Adamawa State residents received information about government infrastructure projects.
3. Assess the extent to which development communication influences residents' acceptance and support of infrastructure projects in Adamawa State.

Conceptual Review

Development Communication

Development communication has been broadly defined as the purposeful use of communication to advance social change and human development. According to Mensah (2021), development communication is the strategic deployment of communication resources to inform, educate and mobilise people towards sustainable development. This definition underlines the intentional nature of the process. It is not spontaneous; it involves careful planning, message design, channel selection and audience engagement. Development communication is about ensuring that people are not only aware of policies or programmes but are persuaded to participate in them (Asemah & Omosotomhe, 2022). It plays a critical role in areas such as public health, environmental protection and education, where behavioural change is essential. For instance, campaigns that encourage vaccination or recycling demonstrate how communication shapes practices that contribute to collective progress. The essence of Mensah's definition lies in the structured, goal-oriented use of communication for measurable change.

In another perspective, Lawal (2022) describes development communication as a participatory dialogue that creates opportunities for communities to express their needs and contribute to decision-making. This view shifts the focus from top-down information delivery to bottom-up interaction. It highlights participation as a central feature. For communication to be effective in development, it must give voice to the marginalised and include them in conversations about issues that affect their lives. This approach fosters trust and enhances the legitimacy of development initiatives. Participation also helps to tailor programmes to local realities, as communities themselves provide insights into the challenges they face. Consequently, development communication is not just about transmitting information but about fostering inclusive conversations that strengthen

ownership and accountability. Lawal's definition stresses that meaningful change emerges when people are actively involved rather than passively informed.

Furthermore, Adebayo (2024) explains development communication as the deliberate provision of information that empowers individuals to make informed choices in social, political and economic spheres. This definition introduces empowerment as a central element. Communication is valuable when it enables people to take control of their lives by providing them with the knowledge and skills they need (Asemah, 2022, 2022a, 2022b). Empowerment here is both cognitive and practical: individuals not only learn about their options but also develop the confidence to act upon them. Empowered citizens are better positioned to demand accountability, resist exploitation and contribute meaningfully to development. Through linking communication to empowerment, Adebayo shows that development is not imposed but facilitated through informed decision-making. This highlights the transformative power of communication when it is used as a tool for enabling agency and independence.

Infrastructural Development

Infrastructural development is widely regarded as the backbone of sustainable economic growth and social transformation. Johnson (2021) defines infrastructural development as a deliberate process through which governments and relevant stakeholders create, expand, and maintain physical facilities such as roads, bridges, public buildings, electricity networks, and water supply systems to enhance societal welfare. This perspective underlines that infrastructure is not merely about constructing physical structures but about laying the foundations for broader socio-economic activities. Roads and transport networks, for instance, enable the movement of goods and people, linking rural areas to markets and urban centres, while electricity and water systems support education, healthcare, and industrial development. Johnson (2021) emphasises that infrastructural development is inherently integrative, serving as the platform upon which other development initiatives, such as education, health, and economic empowerment, can succeed. In essence, infrastructure is a critical enabler that underpins productivity, connectivity, and overall quality of life, making it a non-negotiable component of national progress.

Musa (2022) approaches infrastructural development through the lens of measurement and accountability, arguing that the success of infrastructure projects can only be gauged through systematic monitoring and evaluation. According to Musa, governments must set clear targets, benchmarks, and performance indicators that track the delivery, accessibility, and sustainability of infrastructural investments. For example, road development should not only be measured by kilometres constructed but also by quality, usability, and impact on local communities' economic activities. This approach ensures that infrastructure initiatives do not remain symbolic or politically motivated projects, but instead deliver tangible benefits that improve people's lives. Musa's emphasis on measurable outcomes also highlights the importance of transparency and evidence-based planning in development, ensuring that limited public resources are allocated efficiently and that stakeholders, including citizens, can hold authorities accountable for implementation.

Chike (2023) stresses that infrastructural development cannot be effectively pursued without contextual adaptation to local realities. According to Chike, the success and sustainability of infrastructure projects depend heavily on understanding the unique social, economic, geographical, and cultural characteristics of each community. For instance, road networks in flood-prone or erosion-prone areas require specialised engineering solutions, while electricity distribution must consider population density, consumption patterns, and local technical capacity. Projects designed without local contextualisation often face low adoption, rapid deterioration, or outright rejection by communities, rendering them ineffective. Chike further argues that infrastructure becomes meaningful only when it meets the actual needs of the people it is meant to serve, emphasising that local participation, consultations, and feedback mechanisms are critical in the planning and execution phases.

Literature Review

History of Development Communication Efforts in Adamawa State

The history of development communication in Adamawa State reflects the broader journey of governance and social development in Nigeria. Since its creation in 1991 from the former Gongola State, the state has faced major challenges such as poverty, insecurity, weak infrastructure, and limited access to information. In the early years under Governor Abubakar Saleh Michika (1991–1999), communication was mainly traditional and one-way. Government information reached citizens through Radio Adamawa, town criers, and religious leaders. While these channels helped reach rural communities, they did not allow citizens to give feedback or participate in decision-making (Tanko, 2019). This meant development communication was mostly top-down and limited in interaction.

With the return to democracy in 1999, Governor Boni Haruna (1999–2007) introduced more participatory approaches. His administration focused on youth empowerment, education, and poverty reduction, while civil society organisations became more active in development communication. Groups such as WIN, FOMWAN, and other NGOs supported government messages through community dialogues, advocacy programmes, and town hall meetings. This period allowed more two-way communication, even though government-controlled media still dominated official information flow (Yunusa, 2017). Later, under Governor Murtala Nyako (2007–2014), insecurity from Boko Haram disrupted communication systems, especially in rural areas. Many citizens depended on rumours due to weak official communication structures, while radio remained the main source of information despite its limited reach (Buba & Musa, 2020).

During the brief administration of James Bala Ngilari (2014–2015), communication efforts focused mainly on crisis management, including security updates and humanitarian responses for displaced persons. There was little structured development communication due to ongoing conflict (Sani & Hamman, 2021). Under Governor Mohammed Jibrilla Bindow (2015–2019), infrastructure development became a priority, and communication expanded through social media platforms like Facebook and WhatsApp. However, this digital approach mainly benefited urban residents, while rural communities were still largely excluded due to poor internet access and low digital

literacy (Mustapha, 2022). This period highlighted the communication gap between urban and rural populations in the state.

Under the current administration of Governor Ahmadu Umaru Fintiri (2019–present), development communication has become more structured and intentional. The government uses radio programmes, town hall meetings, religious gatherings, traditional rulers, and social media to inform and engage citizens on infrastructure, education, and health projects. Unlike previous administrations, there is greater effort to include citizen feedback and build public trust (Bello & Danjuma, 2022). Civil society organisations and international partners such as UNDP and Mercy Corps also continue to support grassroots communication efforts (Adamu, 2022). However, despite these improvements, gaps still exist, especially in rural communication access, media reach, and public trust (Abdulrahman, 2020). In all, development communication in Adamawa State has evolved from one-way messaging to more participatory approaches, but full inclusiveness is yet to be achieved.

Role of Development Communication in Achieving Infrastructural Development

Development communication plays a significant role in achieving infrastructural development because it connects government actions with public understanding and participation. It ensures that infrastructure projects such as roads, schools, hospitals, water supply, and electricity are not only implemented but also properly understood and supported by citizens. When development messages are clearly communicated, people are more likely to trust and accept government initiatives. According to Idowu and Odeyemi (2021), communication strongly influences how citizens perceive government projects, which in turn affects their level of acceptance and cooperation. This aligns with the broader view that communication serves as a foundation for linking policy implementation with public engagement (Asemah, 2022b; Asemah & Ekharefo, 2022).

Firstly, development communication serves as an important tool for information dissemination and public enlightenment. It helps to simplify technical details of infrastructure projects and present them in ways that citizens can easily understand. Since many development projects involve complex planning and financial processes, communication bridges the gap between government and the public. Through media platforms, community meetings, and official announcements, citizens are informed about project locations, objectives, and progress. In addition, Anyanwu, Imiti and Anyanwu (2024) note that when people are well informed, they are better positioned to participate meaningfully in development processes and support project implementation. This supports earlier arguments that mass media and communication systems are central to knowledge sharing and public education (Asemah, 2011; Asemah & Asogwa, 2012).

Secondly, development communication promotes citizen participation and feedback in infrastructural development. It provides a platform where individuals and communities can express their views, ask questions, and contribute to decision-making processes. This two-way communication approach improves mutual understanding between government and citizens. Furthermore, it helps policymakers to identify local needs and adjust projects accordingly. As a result, development communication strengthens inclusiveness and increases public trust in government activities, especially when citizens feel that their voices are being considered in development planning. This

participatory dimension is consistent with communication models that emphasise dialogue and interaction in development processes (Asemah, Nwammuo & Nkwam-Uwaoma, 2017; Asemah, Nwammuo & Nkwam-Uwaoma, 2022).

In addition, development communication plays a key role in social mobilisation and public cooperation. Infrastructure development often requires community support, particularly in areas such as land use, relocation, and project maintenance. Through awareness campaigns, town hall meetings, and engagement with traditional and religious leaders, citizens are encouraged to support and sustain development projects. According to Kurgat and Jerop (2023), effective communication can influence public attitudes and enhance cooperation in development programmes. Consequently, it reduces resistance and promotes collective responsibility for infrastructural sustainability. Indigenous and cultural communication systems also play an important role in mobilising communities at the grassroots level (Aríjeníwà, Pepple & Asemah, 2023).

In all, development communication contributes to monitoring, transparency, and accountability in infrastructure development. It enables citizens to report project progress, challenges, and irregularities through both traditional and digital communication channels. However, this requires responsible communication practices to prevent misinformation and ensure accuracy. Moreover, the integration of modern media with indigenous communication systems enhances outreach, especially in rural communities where access to digital platforms may be limited. Asemah, Nkwam-Uwaoma and Santas (2017) observe that traditional communication channels remain highly trusted in many communities and are effective in delivering development messages. In conclusion, development communication serves as a critical link between government and citizens, thereby improving the effectiveness, inclusiveness, and sustainability of infrastructural development.

Theoretical Framework

Behaviour Change Communication Theory

Behaviour Change Communication (BCC) theory developed in the late 1970s from the field of health promotion and later expanded into development communication more broadly (McQuail, 1987). It is based on the idea that communication can be strategically used to influence attitudes, behaviours, and practices in ways that promote public good. Its central assumption is that while knowledge is essential, it is insufficient on its own to transform behaviour. For real change to occur, communication must be tailored, persuasive, culturally sensitive, and consistently reinforced through multiple channels (Piotrow et al., 1997; Asemah, Nwammuo & Nkwam-Uwaoma, 2017). This approach assumes that individuals are not passive recipients of information but active participants whose decisions are shaped by cultural norms, peer influence, and perceptions of risk and benefit.

The theory stresses a gradual process of change. As Ugwuozor and Hui (2020) explain, communication first raises awareness, then builds knowledge, followed by influencing attitudes, and eventually results in behavioural shifts. This has been successfully applied in campaigns against HIV/AIDS, maternal mortality, and environmental degradation across Africa. For example, Musa and Antwi-Boateng (2023) documented how sustained communication campaigns in Ghanaian communities

transformed practices in maternal health, reducing risky behaviours and encouraging healthier lifestyles. This demonstrates that when communication strategies are systematic, targeted, and participatory, they can transform individual behaviours and, by extension, social outcomes.

Recent scholarship has highlighted the relevance of BCC to the Sustainable Development Goals. Anani-Bossman and Blankson (2024) argue that SDG goals such as gender equality, climate action, and quality education all require shifts in attitudes and behaviours. Without communication strategies that challenge harmful cultural norms and promote positive practices, the structural targets of the SDGs may not be achieved. Adepoju and Adekunle (2024) add that while BCC is powerful, its implementation is often costly, requiring continuous investment in media campaigns, interpersonal communication, and community outreach. Moreover, it can be time-consuming as behaviour change is a long-term process, not an immediate outcome. This reinforces the importance of structured and strategic communication planning in development practice (Asemah et al., 2022; Asemah & Nwaoboli, 2024). Similar approaches have been applied in other contexts. Okeke and Alabi (2022), for example, used systems theory to examine Nigerian agricultural programmes and found that communication breakdowns between government agencies, farmers, and international donors weakened policy outcomes.

In the context of this study, behaviour change communication theory is highly applicable because Governor Fintiri's development communication strategies aim to alter public behaviours towards SDG-related practices. For example, improving access to education requires parents to value schooling, while reducing maternal mortality demands that communities adopt modern health-seeking behaviours. Communication strategies such as radio campaigns, grassroots mobilisation, and peer education are vital tools for influencing such changes. This aligns with Abubakar and Hassan (2022), who found that BCC interventions in northern Nigeria significantly improved health-seeking behaviours in rural areas. Thus, the theory enables the present study to assess whether communication strategies in Adamawa State move beyond mere awareness creation to actually facilitating the behavioural transformations required for SDG achievement.

Methodology

The study adopts a survey research design. This design is suitable because it allows the researcher to collect data from a large number of respondents and analyse their opinions on development communication and infrastructural development in Adamawa State. According to Asemah & Nwaoboli (2024), survey design is useful for studying attitudes and perceptions within a population. The population of the study consists of residents from three Local Government Areas (LGAs) in Adamawa State, namely Yola North, Numan, and Ganye. These LGAs were selected to represent urban, semi-urban, and rural settings. The total population of the study is estimated at 711,200 people based on projections from the National Population Commission (2022). From this population, a sample size of 382 respondents was selected using Cochran's formula, and proportionate sampling was used to ensure fair representation across the three LGAs.

The main research instrument used for data collection is the structured questionnaire. The instrument was validated through expert review, while reliability was confirmed using a pilot test conducted in Girei LGA with similar characteristics to the

study area. Data collection was carried out through face-to-face administration with the help of trained research assistants to ensure clarity and high response rate. A total of 382 copies of questionnaire were distributed; however, 23 copies were lost during the process, leaving the valid responses for analysis. Data were analysed using descriptive statistics such as frequency counts, percentages, and mean scores to assess respondents' views on development communication and infrastructural development in Adamawa State. The mean acceptance threshold was 3.0.

Data Presentation

Table 1: Residents' Awareness of Development Communication Strategies Used by Government in Promoting Infrastructure Projects in Adamawa State

Statements	SA (5)	A (4)	UD (3)	D (2)	SD (1)	Total	Mean	Decision
I am aware that government uses radio to inform citizens about infrastructure projects.	132 (37.0%)	118 (33.1%)	56 (15.7%)	33 (9.2%)	18 (5.0%)	357	3.8	Accepted
I know that town hall meetings are used to communicate infrastructure projects in Adamawa State.	120 (33.6%)	112 (31.4%)	65 (18.2%)	38 (10.6%)	22 (6.2%)	357	3.7	Accepted
I am aware that social media is used by government for infrastructure updates.	108 (30.3%)	110 (30.8%)	70 (19.6%)	42 (11.8%)	27 (7.6%)	357	3.6	Accepted

Source: Field Survey, 2026

Table 1 shows a generally high level of awareness among residents regarding development communication strategies. Radio is the most recognised medium, followed by town hall meetings. However, awareness of social media use is comparatively lower, indicating a digital divide between urban and rural residents.

Table 2: Channels Through Which Residents Receive Information on Government Infrastructure Projects

Statements	SA (5)	A (4)	UD (3)	D (2)	SD (1)	Total	Mean	Decision
I receive information about infrastructure projects mainly through radio.	138 (38.7%)	115 (32.2%)	52 (14.6%)	35 (9.8%)	17 (4.7%)	357	3.9	Accepted
I get information through traditional rulers and community leaders.	125 (35.0%)	118 (33.1%)	60 (16.8%)	35 (9.8%)	19 (5.3%)	357	3.8	Accepted
I receive updates through social media platforms like Facebook and WhatsApp.	95 (26.6%)	108 (30.3%)	72 (20.2%)	50 (14.0%)	32 (9.0%)	357	3.5	Accepted

Source: Field Survey, 2026

Table 2 indicates that radio remains the strongest communication channel, followed closely by traditional leaders. Social media is used but is less dominant, especially among rural residents. This confirms that infrastructure communication in Adamawa still relies heavily on traditional and mass media systems.

Table 3: Influence of Development Communication on Residents' Acceptance and Support of Infrastructure Projects

Statements	SA (5)	A (4)	UD (3)	D (2)	SD (1)	Total	Mean	Decision
Government communication increases my support for infrastructure projects.	128 (35.9%)	120 (33.6%)	58 (16.2%)	35 (9.8%)	16 (4.5%)	357	3.8	Accepted
When I understand a project, I am	145 (40.6%)	110 (30.8%)	55 (15.4%)	32 (9.0%)	15 (4.2%)	357	3.9	Accepted

more likely to support it in my community.								
Development communication reduces resistance to government infrastructure projects.	118 (33.1%)	115 (32.2%)	62 (17.4%)	42 (11.8%)	20 (5.6%)	357	3.7	Accepted

Source: Field Survey, 2026

Table 3 reveals that development communication has a strong positive influence on citizens' acceptance of infrastructure projects. Most respondents agree that when they understand government projects, they are more likely to support them. It also reduces resistance and improves trust, although some neutral responses suggest that not all residents are fully engaged.

Discussion of Findings

The findings of this study show that residents of Adamawa State are generally aware of the development communication strategies used by the government to promote infrastructure projects, although the level of awareness is not evenly distributed across all communication channels. Most respondents agreed that the government uses radio, town hall meetings, and social media to share information about infrastructure projects. However, awareness of digital communication, especially social media platforms, is comparatively lower. This suggests that while development communication is present and visible, it is still more effective in traditional media than in digital spaces. The result aligns with earlier studies which argue that in developing societies, communication systems tend to rely more on traditional channels such as radio and community structures due to limited digital access and literacy gaps (Asemah, Nkwam-Uwaoma & Santas, 2017). It also reflects the view that communication effectiveness depends not only on availability of channels but also on accessibility and audience reach.

On the channels through which residents receive information, the findings indicate that radio remains the most dominant source of development communication in Adamawa State, followed by traditional rulers and community leaders. Social media is used, but its influence is weaker compared to mass media and interpersonal channels. This shows that development communication in the state is still largely hybrid, combining both modern and traditional systems. The result supports communication scholarship which emphasises that in rural and post-conflict settings, interpersonal and community-based communication remains highly trusted because of cultural proximity and credibility (Asemah, Nkwam-Uwaoma & Santas, 2017; Idowu & Odeyemi, 2021). It also suggests that government communication strategies are more effective when they pass through trusted local structures, especially in communities where literacy levels and internet access are limited.

The findings further reveal that development communication has a strong influence on residents' acceptance and support of infrastructure projects in Adamawa

State. Most respondents agreed that when they understand government projects, they are more likely to support them, and that communication reduces resistance to infrastructure development. However, some neutral responses suggest that not all residents are fully engaged or consistently reached by these communication efforts. This implies that while development communication is effective in shaping positive perceptions, its impact is moderated by information gaps and uneven participation. The result is consistent with development communication theories which argue that awareness and understanding are key drivers of public participation in development processes (Musa & Aliyu, 2022). It also reflects the participatory communication approach, which stresses dialogue, feedback, and inclusion as essential for building trust between government and citizens (Ahmed & Jibrin, 2022).

Conclusion and Recommendations

This study establishes that development communication positively influences citizens' acceptance and support of infrastructure projects, especially when they understand the purpose and benefits of such projects. However, the study also reveals gaps in digital communication usage, limited feedback mechanisms, and unequal access to information across communities. In all, development communication in Adamawa State is effective but still requires strengthening to achieve full inclusiveness and participation. Based on the findings, the study recommends that:

1. The Adamawa State government should strengthen the use of digital communication platforms while still maintaining strong traditional channels, in order to ensure wider and more inclusive coverage of infrastructure-related information.
2. Government agencies should improve feedback mechanisms by creating more structured community engagement platforms where residents can ask questions, express concerns, and contribute to infrastructure decision-making processes.

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